

Mårtensson, A. (2019). Swedish vocational education and training teachers' role in work with WBL. In F. Marhuenda & M.J. Chisvert-Tarazona (Eds.), *Pedagogical concerns and market demands in VET. Proceedings of the 3rd Crossing Boundaries in VET conference, Vocational Education and Training Network (VETNET)* (pp.337-341) <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.2641844>

Swedish vocational education and training teachers' role in work with WBL

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Abstract

VET teachers play a key role in introducing and connecting students to learning environments of specific workplaces, and in helping students to consolidate learning in schools with learning in the workplace. Therefore, the aim of this paper is to describe and analyze the role played by VET teachers in their work with the students' work-based learning (WBL). The empirical study builds on cases from three of the twelve national vocational programmes in Sweden: Building and Construction, Child and Recreation, and Handicraft. The study consists of 15 interviews with teachers from these programmes. The result shows that depending on to what extent the school or the physical classroom has similarities to the workplace, the VET teacher uses examples from the workplace differently in his or her teaching. The analysis shows two different enactments in how VET teachers talk about creating continuity between school and work.

Keywords

vocational teacher; work-based learning; teacher work

1 Introduction and background

Work-based learning (WBL) has a central position in vocational education and training (VET). However, the organisation of and responsibilities for WBL vary between countries, as does the role of the VET teacher in relation to WBL (Cedefop, 2018). In some countries the workplace has the full responsibility for the WBL parts of VET. In Sweden, VET teachers from vocational schools have a central role and responsibility when it comes to the work-based parts of VET on upper secondary level. They are responsible for planning, grading, and ensuring safety and values in the workplace, but they rarely take part of the day-to-day work in which the student engages in the workplace. The aim of this paper is to describe and analyze the role played by VET teachers in their work with the students' work-based learning (WBL).

The curriculum states that students should be on WBL for at least 15 weeks during the three-year long programme, and some who take the apprenticeship track are 50% or more of the time in the workplace. Out of the three years of the upper secondary school VET programmes, two thirds of the time are vocational subjects including the work-based learning parts.

The research question in this study is:

- How do VET teachers work in school and on the boundary between school and working life to enhance students vocational learning?

The empirical study builds on cases from three of the twelve national vocational programmes in Sweden: Building and Construction (BCP), Child and Recreation (CRP), and

Handicraft (HCP). The study consists of 15 interviews with teachers from these programmes. A thematic analysis was conducted and patterns in the interviews were developed into themes (Boyatzis, 1998; Braun & Clarke, 2008).

The study is theoretically based in Lave and Wenger's (1991) and Wenger's (1998) theory of situated learning with its central concepts' community of practice and legitimate peripheral participation. Particularly the concepts of boundary processes, brokering, and design for learning are of interest in the study to discuss the VET teacher's work.

2 Previous research

Previous research shows that VET teachers use many methods when working with WBL in order to link students' learning to different workplaces with the requirements set by the curriculum. Therefore, the way in which they cooperate and communicate with WBL providers may vary with time and situation (Billett, 2006; Vähäsantanen, Saarinen & Eteläpelto, 2009). Vähäsantanen et al. (2009) unwrap different ways of connecting with the workplace where the individual teacher's thoughts on how to work with the workplace affect the cooperation between school and workplace. The different roles VET teachers take on are relational constructions, and they are defined relative to complementary and interrelated roles. This means that VET teachers' work must be put into a broad context that includes the workplace (Billett, 2008; Isopahkala-Bouret, 2010).

Teaching always comprises meetings. A good relationship between students and teachers is important for learning, and the ability to build relationships with students is vital for all categories of teacher (e.g. Aspelin & Persson, 2011; Langelotz, 2014). The VET teacher, who often interacts with students during long hours at school, has the opportunity to develop a solid base of knowledge about the student (Köpsén, 2014). Swedish research has also shown that teachers see fostering as an important part of education as they want the students to develop and mature, the teachers want to give the students a sense of something to believe in (Berner, 2010; Köpsén, 2014). Widening the students' knowledge and understanding is an important part of the teacher work, and this cannot always be satisfied in the workplace (Berner, 2010).

International research has shown that an emergent teacher task is to connect students with their future community of practice, and that the role of broker is crucial for the stakeholders to come together in a joint enterprise (Willegems, Consuegra, Struyven & Engels, 2016). Previous research in the Swedish context has shown that teachers play a key role in introducing and connecting students to learning environments of specific workplaces, and in helping students to consolidate learning in schools with learning in the workplace (Köpsén, 2014; Lagström, 2012). This broker role, however, puts the teachers into an exposed position as they become accountable by two 'worlds' (Akkerman & Bakker, 2011). In this paper I will also elaborate on how VET teachers work in school and use their vocational experience and students WBL in enhancing students learning.

3 Result

The result shows that the VET teachers' work with WBL takes place both on the boundary between school and workplace, and in school.

5.1 VET teachers work on the boundary between school and work

The work on the boundary concerns activities before and during students' WBL periods. This work can be thematised as 'being a recruiter', 'being a matchmaker', and 'being a firefighter'. 'Being a recruiter' describes the work of finding work placements for all the students. This work ranges from being dependent on the teachers' own social network to arguing for the

importance of students finding their own placements. The school is responsible, but the outcome depends to a great extent on the teacher's own network. 'Being a matchmaker' consists of the task to match each student with a good learning environment at the work place. This work is done with the students' learning as well as their social needs in focus, to match each student with a suitable workplace and supervisor. The teacher's capability to cross boundaries connecting students to suitable workplaces demands that the teacher has knowledge of both the students and the local business. 'Being a firefighter' concerns the emergency work related to problems between the student and supervisor but also the preventive work VET teachers do before WBL, in contact with both students and supervisors. This job, done on the boundary of school and workplace, is a highly complex relational work which puts teachers' relational competence to the test. This boundary crossing and brokering are seldom seen as a teacher's tasks, but for the learner in VET, the teacher's background, network, and relational skills become crucial.

5.2 How WBL is used in classrooms

In school, the teachers' job differs. The results show that depending on to what extent the school or the physical classroom have similarities to the workplace, the VET teacher uses or draws upon examples from the workplace differently in his or her teaching. The analysis shows two different enactments in how VET teachers talk about creating continuity between school and work.

5.2.1 *Connecting workplace to school all the time*

The analysis shows that some teachers consider WBL and connections with workplaces as essential in their in-school teaching. Teachers from CRP represent one group who speaks a lot of the importance of WBL and therefore speaks of it daily in the classroom. For example, before the students are on their first WBL period these teachers point out that they try to make students understand that becoming a pre-school worker or to work in the social sector means a shift in perspective. Before the students first WBL period some teachers use the parable of swimming on dry land. Clara (CRP) says 'I can teach theory in-school before WBL, but after WBL, the students can connect experiences with theory and then I can teach in a different way'. In teaching Camilla (CRP) often uses sayings as 'think of this when on WBL' and in doing activities with the students she says she has to remind them of that 'you can do this yourself at the workplace'. After the students have been on WBL Clara (CRP) continues describing how she uses that experience, 'to get the students motivated in my teaching it is a good thing to connect to their own experiences at WBL'. She figuratively moves between the classroom and the workplace to boost the students' interest, facilitate for learning and create mutual engagement, joint enterprise, and shared repertoire within the community of practice of working life; an understanding for what is not present – practice.

5.2.2 *Connecting not needed – it's easy to move between theory and practice*

In some teachers' descriptions of their work connecting WBL and school they say they rarely talk about WBL in the classroom/workshop. However, the analysis shows that their in-school work is situated in or close to workshops resembling the workplace. To reach closeness to the artefacts of the WBL the teacher instead can ask questions like 'have you seen this tool before?' to get students' attention. Another case where teachers see WBL as helpful is when talking about work ethics; is it ok to wear a crop top at the hairdressing saloon or to show off tattoos, is it ok to take the first available chair in the coffee room at break? When these teachers talk about connecting with the workplace it becomes something else than how they use

WBL, it becomes a description of how they teach. They describe that having a ‘theory’ classroom close to the workshop is a winning concept. If they start teaching in theory or practice isn’t described as important, that varies, it isn’t obvious or important, it depends on many factors.

If you can move between them [theory and practice], then those who don’t get it here [theory room], they’ll get it out there. They get an understanding out there and then they can connect here when they come here again. I wish I could use more reality in theory. (Henrik, HCP)

The teachers describe how they in their teaching explain how to do something starting either in the workshop or the ‘theory classroom’, ending up with some students understanding and some not. They then go to the other site, explain one more time either with the help of practice or theory, and some students now understand while some students have to start working on the task and after that gradually end up understanding. This moving between theory and practice gives students several opportunities to understand and connect theory and practice. The difference between workshop and theory classroom is here interpreted as making the boundary visible even though both sites are in school. The workshop in school is a good substitute for the workplace and therefore there is no need to visualize or discuss WBL in order to create continuity with the community of practice.

4 Discussion

This study contributes to the understanding of VET teachers’ work and brokering between school and working life, and how that differs from the often-described subject teachers’ mainly school-based work. The study shows that the conditions (e.g. the schools similitude to workplace practice) that the VET teachers work under are of great importance for the frames they can act within and create sameness and continuity between school and workplace for students. In relation to the VET teacher training institution it becomes an important task to prepare the teacher students for this boundary crossing and relational work.

The findings show that in two out of the three different programmes in this study (BCP and HCP) it is obvious how much the workshops/classrooms resemble the work place teachers educate for. Teachers create situated learning for the students in a safe environment and the teachers work in a workplace resembling their former, and the students upcoming, work environment. VET teachers and students engage mutually, dressed in work clothes, whether it is with scissors at hand or with hard hats and boots with steel cap, and they engage in creating hairstyles, cabinets or other constructions together. At the third programme, CRP, VET teachers have to create this sameness and continuity through their use of their work experience in talk and school assignments. The different conditions provide different possibilities for the VET teacher to create what is seen as important for learning an occupation. All the teachers have the same goal – but they work under different conditions which gives their work different character. Teachers at the CRP needs to visualize and concretize phenomenon as ‘treat different with respect’ and ‘children with different needs’. When the building and construction teacher can show a foxtail saw and show how to best hold it, the child and recreation teacher can’t do that with ‘a typical 4-year old’.

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Biographical notes

Åsa Mårtensson is a Ph D student and lecturer in Education at Linköping University, Sweden.. Her research interest focus VET teachers work in-school as well as at the workplace. In her work as lecturer she teaches at different teacher training programmes mainly focusing social psychology, education and VET pedagogy and she also conducts further education for active VET teachers. Prior to her academic career, she worked as a VET teacher for 15 years.